

The Study of Themes, Ways and Motivations of Women Empowerment in Dalit Feminism

¹Mrs G. Shakila, Research Scholar, Department of English, Rajeswari Vedhachalam Govt. Arts College, Chengalpattu District, Tamil Nadu, India.

²Dr S. M Shanthi, Research Guide, Assistant Professor, Department of English, Rajeswari Vedhachalam Govt. Arts College, Chengalpattu District, Tamil Nadu, India.

ORCID: ¹<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7008-3524>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5203256

Abstract

Dalit women liberation is a women's activist visual perspective that subsumes questions station and sexual orientation jobs among the Dalit populace and inside women's liberation and the greater women's turn of events. Dalit women face different challenges than women in higher castes in South Asian countries. Dalit feminists advocate for equal rights for Dalit women based on gender, caste and other issues. The current status of women has started protesting against the discrimination and injustices even upon them and are trying to create a female space for themselves. In India caste system legitimizes gender inequality and untouchability. Even though their life is very hard, the women have a life outside their homes, unlike upper-caste, middle-class women who remain inside their homes at all times. We should educate boys and girls alike, showing no difference between them as they grow into adults. The injustices, violence, and inequalities will come to an end, by proving that 'Women can make and women can break'. Dalit women have been functioning throughout past times, even though frequently this has not been reported. At Present, they are the fastness of the Dalit movements in thousands of Indian rural areas. They proceed to a plan of action for a censorious character in the movements for women's rights. However, they are unable to put an end to structural discrimination and exclusion. Violence and impunity are used to keep them in their place. In India, the term 'subaltern' is generally used synonymously with the term 'Dalit', especially focusing their attention on the oppressive structures of caste in the Indian context, which divided people as superior touchables and untouchables or upper castes and lower castes. Today's women have begun challenging to oppose the discrimination and are disagreeable to makeover a female space for themselves. The Dalit women have started searching for the root cause of marginalization against them. Women in this pedagogy bring forward their personal identity as women as well as Dalit.

Keywords: Caste, Dalit, Disputes, Gender, Injustices, Nexus, Violence.

Introduction

Since barely any decades Shudras are known as Dalit. Dalit, a word that refers 'ground' gathers under its umbrella various gatherings that move at the edges. Etymologically, the

word Dalit is gotten from Sanskrit word dalita that signifies 'mistreated'. In Indian socio-social setting 'Shudra' or 'Dalit' are untouchables because of their low level work and the beneath the three classes: Brahman, Kshatriya, and Vaishya. Mahatma Gandhi has given a name 'Harijans' to Shudras, implies individuals of God. Ladies' strengthening assumes an indispensable job in bringing any social change. No general public or country can be viewed as cutting edge without enabled ladies.

Misuse, separation, and brutality are a portion of the key terms related with debilitation. The issue of strengthening of ladies requests for a completely conversation on question of intensity through and through. There is no uncertainty that ladies ought to have the option to appreciate the common opportunity just as Constitutional (lawful) one. It is procedure of self-power, poise, self-assurance, independence, self-decision, sense of pride and self-nobility – bereft of social, political, monetary, social and strict weights. In light of the perspectives on various creators, strengthening could be alluded as access to assets, material prosperity, dynamic force, and the capacity to settle on close to home decisions without pressure. Dynamic reason's for women to change the perspective of system. This is in a manner singular strengthening that is interconnected with the network strengthening, which means transforming oneself at the network level. It implies individuals who practice more noteworthy opportunity in their lives might be greater strengthening. In this manner opportunity and decision are the key recommendations in the journey for strengthening of ladies. One could undoubtedly draw a point that no advancement or progress is conceivable without sexual orientation correspondence in any nation of the world.

a. The Themes of Women Empowerment in Feminism:

I Untouchables

India's Untouchables performed profoundly defiling work that no one else needed to do, for example, getting ready bodies for memorial services, treating leathers, and executing rodents or different bugs. Doing anything with dead cows or cowhides was especially unclean in Hinduism. Under both Hindu and Buddhist convictions, employments that included passing defiled the laborers' spirits, making them unfit to blend with others. A gathering of drummers who emerged in southern India called the Parayan (harijans) were viewed as distant in light of the fact that their drumheads were made of dairy animals cover up. Indeed, even people who had no chance to get out (those bound to watchmen who were both Dalits) been not allowed to be not moved by those of higher classes nor raise the places of society. As a result of their uncleanliness according to Hindu and Buddhist divine beings, they were prohibited from numerous spots and exercises, as appointed by their previous existences.

II Dalit Movements

1. Nair Movement Started under the administration of CV Raman Pillai, K Rama Krishna Pillai and M. Padmanabha Pillai in 1861. Against Brahminic domain, The Malayali Memorial was shaped by Raman Pillai in 1891 and Nair Service Society was set up by Padmanabha Pillai in 1914.
2. Satyashodhak Movement established by Jyotirao Phule in 1873 (Maharashtra). For liberation of low standings, untouchables and widows. Against Brahminic domain.

3. Self-Respect Movement Started under the administration of EV Ramaswami Naicker or Periyar in 1925. Against station framework and one-sided approach of Brahmins. Kudi Arasu diary was begun by Periyar in 1910.

The above mentioned some movements are done for Dalits. Consequently, we can say, the Caste or Dalit Movement in India before autonomy was the resultant of scorn being created by the Brahmanism. As per Brahmanism, Dalit or lower standing is allotted to serve the three Varna which implies Brahmin, Kshatriya and Vaishyas. They don't have option to take advanced education and were denied social-monetary and political status.

b. The Three Ways of Women Empowerment in Dalit Feminism:

I Enhance The Self- Respect

Empower the women around us, and cause them to feel exceptional and solid. Urge our companions to make some noise, ensure they know the estimation of their feelings with the goal that they're never terrified to utilize their voice.

II Bolted Down Pessimism

Women are continually presented to cynicism as they're regularly held to ridiculous measures of excellence showed in magazines, on TV, and all the more as of late via web-based networking media. Internet based life has opened the floor for men, and now and again other women to circle negative remarks about ladies' appearances. Lift women up by taking a position against negative remarks on the web, at the workplace, in school, and any place we go. Battle the cynicism by advancing body energy, knowledge, and realness. Try not to be hesitant to close down antagonism legitimately and truly, our kindred females will value you.

III Be Straight and Authentic

The world has been changed by ladies who met the challenge at hand to battle sexism. While it's critical to share your own story, it's similarly as imperative to tune in to other women accounts and encounters. There are huge amounts of extraordinary assets out there to peruse, tune in, and share ladies' accounts. Reese Witherspoon's Hello Sunshine is a media brand that features female stories through film, composed word, sound, and symbolism. Hi Sunshine likewise has an intelligent month to month book club that includes another female writer every month. Find a workable pace skilled ladies, and offer their moving stories with the people throughout your life.

c. The Three Motivations of Women Empowerment in Dalit Feminism

I Turn Into a Counselor

Whether you find a Counsellorship program in your community or focus on inspiring your friends and sisters, being a mentor is a great way to inspire young women. Form a group of women and encourage them to participate in an empowerment activity.

II Combat against Chauvinism

Stand up for ladies' privileges, and be a piece of the procedure! Welcome the rousing people you know to energize together at your nearby ladies' walk, take your insight to the surveys, compose your delegates, and urge other ladies to join the battle for ladies' privileges.

III Help them in Shelter, Education and Placements:

1. Shelter:

Ladies' asylums help furnish ladies with fundamental needs and social administrations. Contact our neighborhood ladies' safe house to discover what assets they need, and make a gift. Numerous ladies' safe houses offer business workshops, so consider giving your time and enable ladies by helping them impeccable their meeting aptitudes or work understanding.

2. Education

Probably the most ideal ways we can engage young ladies is by supporting their education. At the point when we're furnished with information, we can have any kind of effect. Consider making a commitment to an association that keeps young ladies in school, or discover what supplies a nearby school close to you needs, and make a gift.

3. Placements

Show your help for ladies in your locale by putting resources into organizations run by ladies. Know your value and ensure the ladies in your work environment know theirs. Be fearless, and request what you merit, people in the future of working ladies will bless your heart.

Conclusion

Engaging ladies begins with you. Show your help for the ladies around you, give them they matter, and remind them they're solid. Changing the account for ladies and seeing genuine change is collaboration, so share this rundown with the ladies throughout your life, and urge them to make a move! Show the ladies throughout your life the amount you welcome them by sending a note to say thanks, offering them a commendation, or essentially mentioning to them what they intend to you. . Respect resilient ladies, celebrate various sorts of magnificence, engage ladies with graciousness, and urge ladies to make their desires a reality.

References

- [1] Ambedkar, B.R., 1987 b. The woman and counter-revolution. In B.R. Ambedkar Babsaheb Ambedkar Writings and Speeches, Volume 3. New Delhi: Dr. Ambedkar Foundation, pp. 429–437. Available at: www.mea.gov.in/Images/attach/amb/Volume_03.pdf [last accessed 6 March 2018]
- [2] Batliwala, Srilatha. (1993), Empowerment of Women in South Asia, Concepts and Practices, New Delhi, FAO.
- [3] Beteille, Andre. (1999). Empowerment, Economic and Political Weekly, March 6-13:589-97. Boserup, Ester (1970). Women's Role in Economic Development', New York, St. Martin's Press.
- [4] Boserup, Ester (1970). Women's Role in Economic Development', New York, St. Martin's Press.
- [5] Brinton, M. C. (Ed.). (2001). Women's working lives in East Asia. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- [6] Griffen, Venessa. (ed) (1989). Women, development and empowerment: A pacific

- feminist Perspectives. Kuala Lumpur; Asia and Pacific Development Center.
- [7] Kabeer, N. (1999). Resources, Agency and Achievements: Reflections on the Measurement of Women's Empowerment. *Development and Change*, 30, 435-464.
- [8] Kannabiran, K., 2001. Caste, the academy and Dalit women. *The Hindu*, 20 June. Available at: www.thehindu.com/2001/06/20/stories/05202525.htm [last accessed 8 March 2018].
- [9] Malhotra, A., S.R. Schuler and C. Boender. (2002) Measuring women's empowerment as available in international development. Place: Paper prepared for World Bank.
- [10] Meenu Agarwal, "Are Women in India Empowered Enough?" *Women Empowerment and Globalization—A Modern Perspective*, Kanishka Publishers, Distributors, New Delhi, p.241, 2009
- [11] Pigg, K. E. (2009). Three faces of empowerment expanding in theory of empowerment in community development. Columbia: Department of Sociology, University of Missouri.
- [12] Sinha, Kalpana (ed.) (2000), RR Prasad, Shushama Sahay, "Models for Empowering Women", *Empowerment of Women in South Asia*, AMDISA.
- [13] Velayudhan, M., 2014. The radical traditions and histories of Dalit castes in Kerala: challenges from Hindutva. *Mathrubhumi Weekly*, February 22, p. 28.
- [14] Velayudhan, M., 2016. Dalits and the holy cow. *Leftword Blog*, 26 August. Available at: blog.leftword.com/dalits-theholy-cow/ [last accessed 20 February 2018].

Author (s) Contribution Statement: Nil

Author (s) Acknowledgement: Nil

Author (s) Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.